

ETYMOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF AGRARIAN TERMINOLOGY

Khidirova G.

Teacher at Tashkent State Agrarian University, PhD

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14561352>

Abstract. *This article shows that the etymology of the origin of agricultural terms in German and Uzbek languages consists of original German lexemes, lexemes borrowed from foreign languages and mixed lexemes, and that in Uzbek, mainly, there is a layer of its own and a layer of borrowing. It was also found that in the lexicographic sources of the languages under comparison, lexicographic signs were effectively used to obtain complete information about lexemes in the expression of agricultural terms. The abundance of words borrowed from foreign languages in German and Uzbek, as well as the history of the origin, content, and meaning of the lexeme, are of great importance.*

Keywords: *etymology, lexeme, lexicographic source, lexicon, terminology, borrowed words, agrarian terms.*

Introduction. According to linguists, etymology is considered one of the most important and complex areas of linguistics, it determines the origin of each vocabulary and provides scientific information about the formation of linguistic vocabulary and its origin. The main task of etymological analysis is to determine when, in what language and in what form the vocabulary was formed. Etymology (Greek etymon - truth, true meaning + logos - science, teaching)[1] derived from the Greek word and is a section of linguistics that studies the origin of words. By studying the history of the language, a comparative analysis of the etymology of the lexemes of the language, it will be possible to generalize systematic information about words.

In German linguistics, etymological dictionaries cover the vocabulary that existed in German language of the pre-Christian period and the Middle Ages, and in Uzbek linguistics they are reflected in the Turkic layers. When interpreting words etymologically, the semantic and formal aspects of the lexemes are usually taken into account. Historical and etymological studies have proven that most of the lexemes considered root in the modern Uzbek language are actually fictitious words. From the point of view of content and meaning, in etymological dictionaries, words of cultural and intellectual significance are primarily given their original or true meaning.[2]

Research methodology. Currently, modern electronic etymological dictionaries of German linguistics contain a complete scientific and theoretical base of agrarian terms. Referring to the basic linguistic aspects, Boden m. (land) and Wald m. (forest) examples have been usefully used:

Wald m. (forest) 'große, dist mit Bäumen bestandene Fläsche, Forst', ahd. Wald (VIII Jh.), mhd. Walt 'Wald, Waldgebirge, Baumbestand, Holz, die laubigen Äste und zweige eines Baumes. Wald Wald, forest mountains, tree trunks, wood, deciduous branches and tree branches.

Boden m (land, soil) 'Erdoberfläsche, Grund', ahd. almond (IX Jh.), mkr. breakfast (to the XVII Jh.) bodem, mhd. aus boden, ashshs. almond, mind. bodem (e), aus boddem. Translation: earth, soil (surface of the earth, ground, badam in Old German (9th century), boddem, boden in German in the Middle Ages and modern times (17th century) [3].

Effectively using the capabilities of the native language in enriching the horizons of the agricultural sphere, attention is paid to the following cases:

1. In the lexicon of German and Uzbek languages, agricultural terms are expressed as an integral part of the vocabulary. For example, anorganik olam, oziqlantirish, tuproqshunoslik, agrar, agronom, genetika, yaylovchilik, fermer, broyler, bo‘rdoqi, etc.

2. Not only terms related to agriculture are used as agricultural terms, but also terms related to other areas. For example, taklif, sohibkor, daraja, yetakchi, yig‘im, terim, qaydnoma, baho, xo‘jalik kabi leksemalar. Many of the above terms are used as agricultural terms in the agricultural terminology system.

3. Another source that serves to enrich the vocabulary of the agricultural sector are artificial terms formed with the help of affixes: fermerchilik, pudratchi, lalmikor, podachi, pillakor, uzumchilik, chorvador, bog‘dorchilik, qorako‘lchilik, terimchi. Some of the above-mentioned terms came to Uzbek language from Russian language.

At present, in the system of agricultural terms in the lexicon of Uzbek language, common Turkic, Persian-Tajik, Arabic, Russian terms are also used, for example, hamkor, lalmikor, sohibkor, mexanik, ekolog, agronom, botanika, drenaj. As terms in the agricultural terminology system, lexemes borrowed from foreign languages are used, such as a representatives of ecology, agronomy, botany, drainage.

As for the large share of agricultural terms that entered Uzbek language through Russian, it should be noted that Russian vocabulary influenced local languages during the former Soviet Union and that Uzbek agriculture is a Russian village. This can be explained by the high level of cooperation with the economy in the production, collection and processing of products. The following examples once again prove this: agronom, ekolog, ferma, traktor, kombayn, kultivator, kultivatsiya, baranalash, chekanka, mexanizator, buxgalter and others [4].

Analysis of literature on the topic (Literature review). It is known that agriculture and gardening are the main branches of agriculture, the methods of cultivation and care used in them. The fact that it was passed down from generation to generation served as the basis for the development of agriculture and farming. From ancient petroglyphs to manuscripts, on history, literature, art, chemistry, astronomy, architecture and agriculture - today our libraries contain tens of thousands of books. The terminological system of each natural language is enriched by the functional capabilities of this language. The first and most important source of enrichment of the vocabulary of the literary language is its own working resources. Below is an interpretation of agrarian terms in the dictionary entry "Etymological Dictionary of Uzbek Language", created as a preliminary experiment in Uzbek linguistics. For example, BUZOQ - "cow's cub". The calf has grown up and is plowing. This word is formed by adding the suffix -q to the verb formed by the suffix -a from the word "buz", which in Old Turkic means "birth"; in Uzbek, the vowel a before the consonant q changed to the vowel â: (buz+a =buza-)+q =buzaq > buzâq. Originally, this name meant "animal's child", and later it came to mean "cow's child". The dictionary of Mahmud Kashgari gives the word "buzag‘u" with this meaning: this noun is formed from the verb buza- with the suffix -gu. We have proved our point with one more example. For example, Yelin is an organ of an animal that collects milk. This noun is formed from the Old Turkic verb yel-, meaning "to swell-", with the addition of -(i)n: yel- + v = yelv. Originally the word meant "swelling member", and from this meaning came the meaning "member collecting milk". [5] As can be seen from the examples above, the etymological interpretation of agrarian terms in Uzbek language is given in etymological dictionaries. Determining the number of agrarian terms in etymological dictionaries, creating an etymological dictionary of the agrarian field and its implementation by

scientists is one of the important and necessary tasks. As a result of new reforms carried out in the agricultural sector, as a result of the effective use of modern equipment and technology in agriculture, new terms have entered science and the agricultural sector that caused the enrichment of the vocabulary. There are many examples of such words: ijara korxonasi: ijara, ijarachi, yer ijarasi, mulkiy yollanish; pudratchilik: pudrat, oilaviy pudrat; fermerchilik: fermer, fermer xo'jaligi, dehqon-fermer, fermer ayol, fermer xo'jaligi mulki; kooperativchilik: kooperativ, ishlab chiqarish kooperativi, kollektiv uyushma and others⁷.

Even in the Avesta period, the basis of agriculture was sowing, grain growing and farming, and agriculture was quite developed. In the dictionary "Devonu-lugotit Turk" by Mahmud Kashgari [Kashgari M. Turkish Dictionary. Roof III. - T.: Science, 1960. - B. 82.] one can cite many words related to agriculture and irrigation. For example: alan – flat area, tupraq – soil, tarig'chi – farmer who sows grain, arpa – barley, bug'daj – wheat, danal – harvest of barley and wheat, saj – black rocky ground, urug' – seed, chigit – cottonseed. Many words related to agriculture can be found in the works of Mahmud Zamakhshari "Muqaddimat al-adab" of the 13th century, "Kitab ul-idork lil-lison il atrok" by Abu Hayyan.

In the course of historical and etymological research of the vocabulary of the language, that is, based on the sources of words, terms related to the agricultural sphere can be divided into their own layer and acquired layer. The own layer includes layers of ancient Turkic vocabulary, lexical units of the Turkic-Mongolian language, layers of Uzbek words. The acquired layer includes words borrowed from Persian, Arabic, Russian and other languages. It is advisable to single out such words into separate layers and analyze them. Its own layer consists not only of genetically Turkic words. In the word formation system of Uzbek language, there are cases of widespread use of words that came to Uzbek language from other languages. During the long development of the vocabulary of Uzbek language, many words were formed by adding Uzbek and affixes to words. Agrarian terms are lexemes used since ancient times, and they constitute the lexical wealth of the ancient Turkic clan and tribal languages. The following examples of agrarian terms that became Uzbek, the structure of which consists of more than one word, and the components of which belong to different languages, can be given:

1. Uzbek + Tajik + Uzbek: sug'orma dehqonchilik, ekinzor, qishki damba, suvdarvoza.
2. Persian + Uzbek: dehqon xo'jaligi, polizchilik, xirmonjoy, mirobboshi.
3. Uzbek + Arabic: yer ijarasi, ariq marzasi, qirg'oq marzasi.
4. Uzbek + Russian + Persian: bosh kanal shoxobi, zax qochiruvchi kanal.
5. Arabic + Uzbek : ziroatchi, shirkatchilik, ijarachi.
6. Tajik + Uzbek + Arabic: dehqonchilik madaniyati.
7. Arabic + Tajik: aravakash, zarbdor, mulkdor, hosildor, g'allakor.
8. Uzbek + Russian: bosh agronom, donchilik brigada.
9. Russian+Arabic: agrar islohat.
10. Russia+Uzbek: pudratchi, fermerchilik, chizillash, seleksiyachi.
11. Persian + Uzbek : Bog'chilik, mevachilik, sabzavotchilik, polizchilik.

As it can be seen from the examples given, agricultural terms are mixed words with Uzbek, Arabic, Tajik and Russian words.

Agricultural terms in their development develop not only due to words belonging to their own layer, but also due to the long-term existence and development of dictionaries in this area, as

well as borrowed words. In the course of studying agricultural terms, it became known that many words from Persian-Tajik language were borrowed into Uzbek language, and also Russian and Arabic languages left a significant mark on the vocabulary of Uzbek language.

Agrarian terms adapted from Arabic to Uzbek: anhor, ijara, mulk, vodi, sohil, hovuz, maydon, hashar, hosil, g'alla, tanob, nav and etc. During the Timurid era, the attitude towards property improved even more. Since this period, such words and phrases as mulki devon-davlat yerlari, mulk-xususiy yerlar, mulki vaqf-madrasa va masjidlar tasarrufidagi yerlar have entered the dictionary of agrarian terms. In the pre-Timurid period, there were mainly three types of land ownership: Sultoni mulk, mulk and vaqf yerlar. Terms borrowed from Arabic related to land ownership and property during the Timurid period can be divided into three groups. These are terms denoting state lands, terms denoting vaqf lands, and terms denoting private lands.

The vocabulary of agricultural terms includes a large number of words and phrases borrowed from Russian language directly or partially. Examples: pomidor, kartoshka, petrushka, traktor, avtomobil, ammiakli selitra, traktor plugi, kaliyli o'g'it, mineral o'g'itlar, meliorativ choralar, artemizian quduq, vegetatsiya davri, agrotexnik melioratsiya, sug'orish melioratsiyasi, kollektivchilik, kollektiv, kollektivlashtirmoq, kollektivchi, fermer, fermer xo'jaligi, arenda, irrigatsiya, gidrotexnika, gidrotexnik, lotok, kanal, vodokanal, nasos, kollektor, agronom, agrotexnika, aprobatsiya, seleksiya, geksaxloran, fosfor, azot, bakteriya, parazit, karantin, kultivator and etc.

Conclusion/Recommendations. By summarising it should be suggested that the existence of agriculture since prehistoric times confirms that agricultural terms have a thousand-year history and have formed as a system in modern linguistics. However, the vocabulary of this area is considered one of the linguistically poorly studied areas of Uzbek linguistics. Many issues still need to be resolved in the agricultural lexicon. In connection with the period of formation of the vocabulary of this area, the origin of individual words, the identification of sources of its enrichment, and the compilation of dictionaries of terminology in this area are of great importance in linguistics. After gaining independence, much attention was paid to agriculture and much work was done to develop it. New forms of management appeared, such as companies, tenant partnerships, peasant farms, farms, and a cluster system. Family contracting has become widespread in agriculture, and attention was paid to the development of farmsteads. One of the most pressing problems now is the transition of agriculture to a cluster system and the development of this system to achieve full-fledged development of agriculture. Lexemes are acquired in agriculture not only through written sources, but also through oral communication of Uzbek, Tajik, Arab, Russian peoples with each other, trade and agriculture.

REFERENCES

1. Khodjiev A. Explanatory Dictionary of Linguistic Terms. - T.: OME, 2002. - P. 19.
2. DUDEN. Das große Wörterbuch der deutschen Sprache in 6 Bänden. - Mannheim/Vienna/Zurich: Bibliographisches Institut, 1997. -P.2992.
3. Kluge F. Etymologisches Wörterbuch der deutschen Sprache. - Berlin: Union, 2002. -1091 p.
4. Jabborov H. Agricultural vocabulary of the Uzbek language. - T.: Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Publishing House "Science", 2011. -P. 5.
5. Rakhmatullaev Sh. Etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language (Turkish words) -T.: University, 2000. -P. 65.

6. Sinyagina I., Bukharkina V., Vasilyeva G., Pozharsky V. German-Russian agricultural dictionary. About 110,000 terms. 2nd edition, revised. -M.: Russian language, 1987. -P.743.
7. Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language starting with E. Edited by A. Madvaliyev. - T.: State scientific publishing house, 2006-2008. P. 61.
8. Koshgari M. Turkish dictionary. Roof III. -T.: Science, 1960. -P. 82.